

21NRM06 EMC-STD

D4: Report on the assessment of the measurement quality expected when utilising the time domain measurement techniques based on direct sampling according to CISPR 16 including i) overview of commercially available receivers and their capabilities discussed through the scope of the signal processing algorithms ii) estimations of uncertainty, measurement accuracy and time-efficiency as well as information on the ability to intercept the worst-case scenario and the potential associated benefits and trade-offs of the system

This report to include practical use cases that are relevant for CISPR\CIS\A and CISPR\CIS\B

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Abbreviations

ADC	Analog-to-digital converter
AV	Average (detector)
AWG	Arbitrary waveform generator
CISPR	Comité International Spécial des Perturbations Radioélectriques
CW	Continuous wave
DAC	Digital-to-analog converter
DC	Direct current
DFT	Discrete Fourier transform
EM	Electromagnetic
EMC	Electromagnetic Compatibility
EMI	Electromagnetic Interference
ENOB	Effective number of bits
EUT	Equipment under test
FD	Frequency domain
FFT	Fast Fourier transform
GaN	Gallium nitride (semiconductor)
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
LISN	Line Impedance Stabilizing Network
OL	Overlap factor
PDF	Probability distribution function
PK	Peak (detector)
PWM	Pulse-width modulation
QP	Quasi-peak (detector)
RBW	Resolution bandwidth
RTSA	Real time spectrum analyser
SMPS	Switched mode power supply
STFT	Short-time Fourier transform
TD	Time-domain
WL	Window length

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Executive summary

This document describes the assessment of the measurement quality expected when utilising the time domain measurement techniques according to CISPR 16. The report includes an overview of the commercially available measurement instrumentation and its capabilities, discussed through the scope of the signal processing optimisations developed, as well as the estimation of uncertainty, measurement accuracy, time-efficiency, and information on the ability to intercept the worst-case scenario and the potential associated benefits and trade-offs of the system.

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1. Introduction

Two approaches are primarily employed regarding the electromagnetic emission measurement instruments according to the CISPR standard method [1]. The classical approach uses receivers with superheterodyne architecture, which allows for large dynamic range even at high frequencies due to its high scalability. On the other hand, FFT-based receivers digitally process the emissions time-domain data to obtain accurate spectrum estimates while accelerating the frequency scans and allowing for real-time measurements.

The frequency-swept approach used by superheterodyne receivers is inherently slow and unsuitable for measuring short-time emission events and time-variant electromagnetic interference (EMI), resulting in potential detection errors and underestimating actual disturbance levels. Some real examples of time-varying emissions sources include those arising from different operation modes, such as the acceleration/deceleration of electric motors [2], [3], or spread spectrum (SS) based pulse width modulation (PWM) techniques used in modern switch mode power supplies (SMPS) [4].

The development of time-domain EMI measurement systems has transformed electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) testing, offering faster and more detailed signal analysis compared to conventional frequency-domain approaches. Important milestones in the development of the time-domain EMI measurements approach are indicated in Section II below. Among the main advantages of time-domain receivers that have been recognized in recent studies are the following. First, they shorten the test duration by capturing all necessary data over a single operating cycle of the equipment under test (EUT) [5]. Moreover, implementing the time-domain EMI measurements approach can help overcome the challenges of in situ electromagnetic emissions assessments, as shown in [6], [7] and facilitates synchronous multi-channel acquisitions within a single system as demonstrated in [8] for the case of multi-line conducted emissions tests, or in [9] and [10] where multiple antennas are used to measure H-Field and E-Field simultaneously. Furthermore, time-domain receivers enable spectrogram visualizations, aiding in EMI characterization and classification.

The numerous advantages of the time-domain EMI measurement approach are driving its increasing adoption; but still, its integration into compliance testing remains challenging due to the lack of explicit standardization. For example, the CISPR 16-1-1 standard [1] covers FFT-based receivers in a broad manner; however, implementations based on direct sampling instruments are not explicitly mentioned. Moreover, the said standard only gathers requirements that are common for any measuring receiver architecture under a black box approach. This means there are no specific calibration requirements for time domain EMI receivers, and some controversy remains concerning different measuring receiver architectures providing non-identical measurement results. Furthermore, previous studies have only provided limited validation of these systems, often focusing on individual performance metrics rather than a comprehensive, multi-level assessment.

To bridge this gap, we present a multi-level validation approach that systematically evaluates direct sampling time-domain EMI receivers against industry-standard frequency-domain EMI receivers. Unlike previous studies, this paper introduces a comprehensive validation strategy that includes the following stages: establishing a meta-analysis of calibration data to verify baseline accuracy, conducting controlled signal experiments to test time-domain EMI receiver performance across different CISPR frequency bands, and benchmarking real-world EMI measurements using complex load cases (e.g., DC/DC converters with spread spectrum techniques). Thus, validation is achieved by comparing FFT-based direct sampling receivers and other measurement receiver architectures in experiments organised at three levels of complexity. In this context, the complexity of the experiment is related to the number of parameters required to define the reference signal. It provides empirical evidence to support the inclusion of direct sampling EMI receivers in future EMC standardization efforts. In total, this work reports five experiments conducted by three independent groups and institutions, and considers nine different measuring receiver models. By addressing these gaps, this work ensures the reliability of direct sampling EMI receivers and lays the foundation for their broader adoption in compliance testing and EMC research.

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2. Methodology

This section describes the measurement setups, procedures followed, and intended characteristics of the measured signals for each experiment. Experiments are arranged in the order of increasing complexity of the measured signal and identified through a code. The independent teams involved in each experiment are labelled as “A”, “B”, and “C” for INTA, EMC Barcelona, and the University of Twente, respectively. The summary of each experiment is given in Table 1, while the specific details are given in the following subsections.

Table 1. Summary of the experiments.

Code	Experiment description	Team
E0	Meta-analysis of calibration data of EMI receivers using standard reference signals.	A
E1.1	Verifications using controlled modulated signals. Pulse modulated sinewave, CISPR bands B to D.	A+B
E1.2	Verifications using controlled modulated signals. Alternative signals, CISPR band A.	C
E2.1	Realistic emissions measurements using a commercial off-the-shelf (COST) DC/DC buck-boost converter.	A+B
E2.2	Realistic emissions measurements using a DC/DC GaN converter with alternative PWM.	C

This study considers various instruments from different manufacturers and architectures, as depicted in Table 2 and Fig. 1. To facilitate the presentation of the results, the EMI receivers in the selected sample have an associated identification code (ID). Receivers ID R1 and R2 are those based on direct sampling methods as described in [29]. It must be noted that all experiments use at least three different receivers, and the direct sampling approach is present in all experiments at least through one of the samples.

Table 2. List of measuring receivers considered during the experiments. The instruments marked (*) are those based on direct sampling implementations. The symbol (Δ) highlights CISPR 16-1-1 compliance according to specifications, at least in the frequency range of the experiments.

ID	Measuring receivers	E0	E1.1	E1.2	E2.1	E2.2
R1	emiGO(*,Δ) + R&S RTO64 DC - 3 GHz	✓	✓		✓	
R2	emiGO(*,Δ) + PS5444D DC - 200 MHz	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
R3	R&S ESI(Δ) (20 Hz - 40 GHz)		✓			
R4	R&S ESW(Δ) (1 Hz - 8GHz)		✓		✓	
R5	R&S ESW(Δ) (1 Hz - 26.5GHz)	✓				
R6	R&S ESW(Δ) (1 Hz - 44GHz)	✓				
R7	Keysight N9038B MXE (Δ) (3 Hz - 44GHz)	✓				
R8	R&S ESPI (9 kHz - 7GHz)			✓		✓
R9	Signal Hound BB60C (9 kHz - 6GHz)			✓		✓

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Fig. 1 Photograph of some of the receivers from Table 2.

2.1 E0 - Meta-analysis of EMI receivers calibration data

This experiment used calibration data extracted from certificates produced by ISO/IEC 17025 accredited laboratories. For the calibration of measuring receivers, reference signals are typically sine waves and baseband pulses. That means they have low complexity and are easily generated with lower measurement uncertainty in comparison to the signals used in the rest of the experiments. In particular, we focused on the baseline parameters required in [1]. It is important to note that all receivers considered comply with CISPR 16-1-1 according to their specifications. Calibration data confirmed this. However, we wanted to verify how closely direct sampling implementations performed in comparison to the high-end receivers under these calibration conditions.

2.2 E1.1 - Pulse modulated sinewave, CISPR bands B to D

In this experiment, we measured pulse modulated sinewaves according to the characteristics defined in Table 3. The setup was configured with the output of the signal generator directly connected to the input of the measuring receiver. The source was a vector signal generator model Agilent E4438C (250 kHz - 6 GHz). This signal allows for the verification and comparison of the response of the weighting detectors at a given frequency. Tested frequencies are found in CISPR bands B to D. This experiment follows a full factorial design, with a total of 90 measurements executed using the four distinct receivers considered.

Table 3. Summary of the experiments.

Parameters	Value
Level (dB μ V):	66
Tested frequency, (MHz):	1, 10, 100, 500
Pulse duration, τ (μ s):	10, 20, 50
Pulse period, T (μ s):	100, 1000

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2.3 E1.2 - Alternative generated signals, CISPR band A

For the modulated signals in Table 4, this experiment evaluates the performance of measuring receivers within the CISPR band A. The test signals were chosen to comprise some of the characteristics of the emissions of power converters. Test signals E1.2.(1,2,3) have a constant frequency content, while E1.2.(4,5) change their frequency content over the measurement time. The test signals are generated by an arbitrary waveform generator (AWG) Teledyne T3AFG120. The measurement time is set to 100 ms to ensure an integer number of periods for all test signals. Then the measurement outputs of R2 and R9 are compared with R8, which is taken as the reference.

Table 4. Summary of the experiments.

ID	Test signal	Parameters
E1.2.1	Sinewave	100 kHz, 1 V (RMS)
E1.2.2	Multitone	20/40/60/80/100/120/140 kHz, 100 mV (RMS) each
E1.2.3	Square pulse	20 kHz, 1 V (PPK)
E1.2.4	Chirp pulse	80 kHz - 120 kHz, 1 V (RMS), $t_{spr} = 20$ ms.
E1.2.5	Spread-spectrum square signal	18 kHz - 22 kHz, 1 V (PPK), $t_{spr} = 20$ ms.

2.4 E2.1 - Emissions of a COST DC/DC buck-boost converter

The conducted emissions of the device reference AZDelivery XL-4016E1 are measured using the setup presented in Fig. 2. The device input voltage is set to 12 V, the output voltage is adjusted to 5 V, and the switching frequency is fixed at approximately 64 kHz. The device is loaded with a resistor (1 Ω - 200 W) cooled by a fan. The transducer used to measure the disturbance voltage on the positive and negative input lines is a SCHWARZBECK V-LISN model NNBL 8226-2. The radiofrequency current is also measured in both lines using the probes MD 4070 (4 kHz - 400 MHz) from TESEQ and 9250-1N (10 kHz - 450 MHz) from Solar Electronics Company. The measurement parameters for R1, R2, R3, and R4 were set according to the MIL-STD-461G standard guidelines.

Fig. 2 E2.1 - The schematic of the measurement setup. Multi-channel measurement is possible for the oscilloscope-based implementations (R1 and R2). For R4, measurements are performed sequentially, one line at a time.

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2.5 E2.2 - Emissions measurement of a DC/DC GaN buck converter using spread spectrum modulation

The conducted emissions of a CoolGaN™ 600V half-bridge evaluation board are measured using the setup presented in Fig. 3. This device circuit is a buck converter based on Gallium Nitride (GaN) transistors loaded with 8.2 Ω. This GaN converter is controlled by the development board LAUNCHXL-F28379D using MATLAB Simulink. Three types of switching frequency modulation are shown in Table 5. Two of them have been used to spread the spectrum of the emissions [4]. The GaN converter is supplied through the LISN model TEKBOX TBOH01 5 μH. The receivers used to measure the emission are R2, R8, and R9, as shown in Table 2. Also, the RF current probe model F-33-2 (1 kHz – 250 MHz) from the positive line measures the normal mode current (INM). The schematic of the test setup is presented in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3 The schematic of the measurement setup. The INM is measured via R2, R8, and R9 receivers.

Table 5. E2.2 - Spread spectrum modulation characteristics.

ID	PWM Type	Parameters
E2.2.1	Continuous	20 kHz, Steady
E2.2.2	Linear	18 kHz - 22 kHz, Period variation of 20 ms.
E2.2.3	Random	18 kHz - 22 kHz, Period variation of 20 ms.

3. Results

In this section, the results of all experiments are presented in an orderly manner from E0 to E2.2. For clarity reasons, only the most representative results are reported in what follows. The data of test conditions that have been omitted is available upon request.

E0 - Meta-analysis of EMI receivers calibration data

The meta-analysis of the measuring receivers' calibration data is presented below. Due to the lack of standardization in the format for presenting such calibration results, most certificates reported the results differently. Therefore, the original data was normalized and plotted as in Fig. 4 to

Fig. 7 to facilitate the necessary comparisons.

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Fig. 4 corresponds to the sinewave voltage level error in CISPR band B when a reference CW signal is fed to the receiver. Typically, the target amplitude level is 66 dB μ V. For each receiver, the calibration points are plotted, along with error bars corresponding to the measurement uncertainty.

Fig. 4 E0 - CISPR Band B. Sinewave level accuracy calibration results. Amplitude level of the reference signal 66dB μ V. The frequency of the calibration points might be different for each receiver unit.

Next, we present some calibration results of the response to pulses. In Fig. 5, the focus is on the quasi-peak (QP) detector error when a pulsed signal at a reference repetition rate (25 Hz) is applied. On the other hand, Fig. 6 shows the error in the peak (PK) to quasi-peak ratio (PK/QP) at the said pulse repetition frequency (PRF). The absolute and relative responses to pulses are expected to be flat in a given CISPR band for a given PRF. For the reported cases, calibration points and the measurement uncertainty are indicated in the plots.

Fig. 5 CISPR Band A. Response to pulses. QP detector deviation at a pulse repetition frequency of 25 Hz. absolute calibration.

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Fig. 6 E0 - CISPR Band B. Response to pulses. PK/QP ratio deviation at a pulse repetition frequency of 25 Hz.

With respect to the resolution bandwidth (RBW) filter characteristics,

Fig. 7 shows the 1.5 dB, 6 dB and 20 dB decay points and the RBW filter mask requirement for band A. The standard does not fix the test frequency, so this is defined by the calibration laboratory. RBW filter characteristics are very similar in all the models considered in the analysis.

Data shows that direct sampling implementations do not perform differently (significantly better or worse) from receiver models using other architectures. The results for the bands or test conditions not shown above exhibit the same behaviour and lead to equivalent conclusions.

E1.1 - Pulse modulated sinewave, CISPR bands B to D

Fig. 8 to Fig. 10 show the error associated with the measurements obtained for each device, detector, and frequency under evaluation. It should be noted that the R2 data is not presented for the 500 MHz frequency due to the bandwidth limitations of the device. The error limits of the graphs are between ± 1.5 dB, as this is the CISPR 16-1-1 tolerance. No significant discrepancies were observed between the R3 and R4 errors and the oscilloscope-based implementations R1 and R2. In most cases, the error remains consistently within ± 0.5 dB for all devices and detectors. The most prominent exception of this is exemplified in Fig. 10, at 100 MHz and 500 MHz, where larger deviations in the average detector were found. In all cases, test results are within CISPR tolerance.

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Fig. 7 E0 - Selectivity of the resolution bandwidth filter. CISPR Band A.

Fig. 8 E1.1 - Test condition: $\tau = 20 \mu\text{s}$, $T = 1 \text{ ms}$.

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Fig. 9 E1.1 - Test condition: $\tau = 10 \mu\text{s}$, $T = 100 \mu\text{s}$.

Fig. 10 E1.1 - Test condition: $\tau = 50 \mu\text{s}$, $T = 1\text{ms}$.

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Fig. 11 E1.1 - Test condition: $\tau = 50 \mu\text{s}$, $T = 1\text{ms}$.

E1.2 - Alternative generated signals, CISPR band A

In this subsection, first, the noise level measurement results of the used receivers are presented, then results E1.2.3 and E1.2.5 are selected for demonstration as representing the most remarkable cases.

- 1) Noise level: Fig. 12 shows the noise floor of the receivers under test with the limit provided by MIL-STD 461G. All receivers perform noise level results at least 30 dB μV less than the limit line. The noise level of the R8 can be lower if the level of the used attenuator is reduced. However, this results in a lower measured voltage range. For consistency, Fig. 12 displays the noise level measurement results with uniform settings applied across all measurements.
- 2) Signals with stable frequency content: In this subsection, the results of the three test signals with stable frequency content are reviewed together. For example, Fig. 13 presents the results of the square signal measurement via R2, R8 and R9 receivers at seven specific frequencies. Since R8 is considered the reference device at this stage, within each pair (R2/R8 and R9/R8), the differences between their outputs at each specific frequency were found using equations (1) and (2).

$$\Delta_{R2,j} = S_{R8,j} - S_{R2,j}, \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta_{R9,j} = S_{R8,j} - S_{R9,j}, \quad (2)$$

where, $S_{R2,j}$, $S_{R8,j}$, and $S_{R9,j}$ are the amplitude values measured via R2, R8 and R9 receivers at specific frequencies j . Then, the maximum and average differences for each test signal and detector are found by 3 and 4.

$$\Delta_{\text{MAX},i} = \max(\Delta_{ij}), \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta_{\text{AVE},i} = \text{mean}(\Delta_{ij}), \quad (4)$$

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where i corresponds to receivers under test. Calculated Δ_{MAX} and Δ_{AVE} are listed in Table 6. As receiver R9 does not provide the average and quasi-peak detector, therefore R9 results are presented only for the peak detector. Within the E1.2.1 and E1.2.2 receivers R2 and R9 show the results with a maximum deviation of 0.43 dB from reference receiver R8 for all detectors. In E1.2.3 the deviation becomes more significant, the average values in the R2/R8 pair increase up to 2 dB and the maximum deviation exceeds 3 dB for average and quasi-peak detectors. These significant deviations can be explained by the level of the measured signal at 120 kHz close to the noise level of the receivers used as can be seen in Fig. 13.

Table 6. E1.2 - Maximum and average differences between receivers for the alternative signals with stable frequency content

ID	Detector	R2/R8 (dB)		R9/R8 (dB)	
		Δ_{MAX}	Δ_{AVE}	Δ_{MAX}	Δ_{AVE}
E1.2.1	PK	0.08		0.08	
	AVE	0.08		-	
	QP	0.34		-	
E1.2.2	PK	0.14	-0.09	0.18	-0.09
	AVE	0.15	-0.10	-	
	QP	0.43	-0.37	-	
E1.2.3	PK	1.67	-0.26	13.69	-4.39
	AVE	4.35	-1.00	-	
	QP	4.47	-2.02	-	

- 3) Signals with time-variant frequency content: The measurement of time-variant signals needs to be analyzed over a spectrum of frequencies rather than at distinct ones. However, the data collected from different receivers can differ in length, even though they need to be uniform for effective cross-comparison. To achieve this, the results from R8 and R9 are linearly resampled to match the length of the R2 data set, ensuring the consistency of the original output behavior. For example, in Fig. 14, the resampled results of the chirp signal (E1.2.4) are presented. Although the set amplitude of the signal is 1 VRMS (120 dB μ V), all receivers resulted in lower values. It is the expected measurement result of the signal with the variant frequency content over the measurement time. The probability density function (PDF) and histogram clearly visualize the difference between the measurements received. They are presented in Fig. 15.

Fig. 12 E1.2 - Noise floor of the R2, R8 and R9 receivers.

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Fig. 13 E1.2.3 - Measurement results of the square signal. Peak detector.

Fig. 14 E1.2.4 - Measurement results of the chirp signal.

Fig. 15 E1.2.4 - The PDF of the chirp signal measurements.

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From Fig. 14 and Fig. 15, it is clear that R2 results in a closer match to R8 output in comparison to R9; only several 0.5 dB deeps are noticed. For these resampled data at the frequency range of interest (from 80 kHz to 120 kHz), the differences within pairs R2/R8 and R9/R8 are found according to (1) and (2). The average difference (\bar{d}) and the standard deviation of differences (s_d) are defined, as well as the difference between the mode values (Δ_{MODE}) seen in Fig. 13.

Calculated values characterizing differences within pairs R2/R8 and R9/R8 for different detectors are presented in Table 7. Average differences over the frequency range of interest are much lower than 3 dB for all detectors. The mode value of the R8 and R2 results differs by 0.01 dB. Oppositely, R9 results in a mode value 0.14 dB higher. The low value of the s_d indicates that R9 results are consistently higher than R2 results throughout the frequency range.

The spectrum measurement of the E1.2.5 has four characteristic frequency spans, as shown in Fig. 16. Each frequency span is processed separately in the same way as for the chirp signal above. The differences in peak detector measurements in R2/R8 and R9/R8 pairs are found, and for the R2/R8 pair, the results of the average and quasipeak detectors are compared and analysed. Then, the maximum and average differences over four spans are found. Table 8 summarises the average values that characterize the differences between R2 and R9 measurements from R8.

Table 7. E1.2.4 - Receivers comparison for the chirp signal.

Receiver	R9/R8	R2/R8	
Detector	PK	PK	QP
Δ_{MODE} , (dB)	-0.14	0.01	0.85
\bar{d} , (dB)	-0.14	0.07	-0.08
s_d , (dB)	0.05	0.11	1.13

Fig. 16 E1.2.5 - Square signal with variant modulated frequency measurements. Peak detector.

The average and maximum deviations between measurements, as well as the standard deviation, demonstrate the high accuracy of using the R2 receiver. The calculated deviations are in the range of ± 1 dB.

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Table 8. E1.2.5 - Receivers comparison for the square signal with variable modulated frequency

Receiver	R9/R8		R2/R8	
Detector	PK	PK	AVE	QP
Δ_{MODE} , (dB)	-0.19	-0.08	0.59	-0.12
\bar{d} , (dB)	-0.26	-0.05	-0.06	-0.30
s_d , (dB)	0.11	0.15	1.01	0.32

E2.1 - Emissions of a COST DC/DC buck-boost converter

The photograph of the measurement setup is shown in Fig. 17. The results of this experiment are structured according to the most relevant observations made during the data analysis stage, including considerations about harmonic voltage level accuracy, broadband voltage level accuracy, resonances, and noise floor. In particular, Fig. 18 shows the spectrum comparison between the R1, R2 and R4 for the positive line (OUT 0) of the LISN, and this case is used to exemplify the general observations.

- 1) Harmonic voltage level accuracy: Fig. 19 to Fig. 21 show R4 deliver a coarser frequency resolution than R1 and R2 for the same basic settings. This might be explained by the type of frequency interpolation used, including the interpolation ratios and algorithms. R1 and R2 use the Akima method, while R4 applies linear interpolation.
- 2) Broadband voltage level accuracy: Fig. 22 shows the broadband emission spectrum measured when the resolution bandwidth is larger than the distance between individual harmonic components. An excellent agreement is observed in the spectrum amplitude for all receivers considered. To quantify the difference between R4 (reference) and the oscilloscope-based systems (R1 and R2), the deviations are calculated as

$$\bar{\Delta}_1 = S_{R4} - S_{R1}, \tag{5}$$

$$\bar{\Delta}_2 = S_{R4} - S_{R2}. \tag{6}$$

Fig. 23 compares the approximated distribution of the deviations in (5) and (6) using a histogram format. The mean values of the calculated errors in that frequency range $\bar{\Delta}_1$ and $\bar{\Delta}_2$ are very close to 0 dB, being -0.16 dB and 0.06 dB, respectively.

Fig. 17 Photograph of the COST DC/DC buck-boost converter

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Fig. 18 E2.1 - Conducted emissions, positive line (LISN OUT 0).

Fig. 19 E2.1 - Zoom of harmonic at 189 kHz.

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Fig. 20 E2.1 - Zoom of harmonic at 762.5 kHz.

Fig. 21 E2.1 - Zoom of harmonic at 1.138 MHz.

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Fig. 22 E2.1 - Broadband emissions in the range 30 MHz - 50 MHz.

Fig. 23 E2.1 - Difference in the amplitude levels for broadband emissions in the range 30 MHz - 50 MHz.

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- 3) Resonances: Around resonances, the spectrum amplitude changes rapidly with frequency. In this case, some examples of small resonances are found in Fig. 22. Table 9 shows the amplitude level and frequency of both resonance peaks. In those two cases, we found a difference of less than 0.5 dB and 40 kHz.

Table 9. E2.1 - Analysis at the resonance frequencies.

	R1	R2	R4	R1	R2	R4
Level, (dB μ V)	57.07	56.62	56.77	57.76	58.21	58.37
Frequency, (MHz)	30.74	30.72	30.70	43.29	43.31	43.33

- 4) Noise floor: Fig. 24 shows the noise floor of R1, R2 and R4 compared with a conducted emissions limit; in this case, we used the limit corresponding to the CE102 test according to the MIL-STD-461G. According to the data, noise levels are sufficiently low. However, we found out that R4 in its by intended configuration (without preamplifier and with 10 dB of internal attenuation) delivered the higher noise floor.

Fig. 24 Noise floor and standard limit comparison.

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E2.2 - The validation through the EMI measurements of the DC/DC GaN converter.

The results of the EMI measurements of the DC/DC GaN converter with different PWM (see Fig. 25) are presented in this subsection. In this case, the EMI is presented via normal mode current I_{NM} , and its measurements are performed via an RF current probe.

Fig. 25 Photograph of the DC/DC GaN converter

1) *Continuous Pulse Width Modulation*: The continuous PWM with a fundamental frequency of 20 kHz applied for the DC/DC GaN converter resulted in EMI with seven specific frequencies below 150 kHz, similar to the spectrum of the square signal, presented in Fig. 13. In Fig. 26, the measurement results of the peak detector are presented. The deviations of the R2 and R9 output from R8 measurements are defined by 1 and 2. The maximum and average deviations for the three detectors are listed in Table 10.

Fig. 26 E2.2.1 - Continuous PWM. Peak detector.

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The receiver R2 results in a uniform deviation from the reference R8 output for all detectors, ranging from 0.43 dB to 0.7 dB. Meanwhile, R9 results in a higher deviation from R2 by up to 2.96 dB at 20 kHz.

2) *Spread Spectrum Pulse Width Modulation*: A spread spectrum technique is used to reduce the emission detected in the standard emission tests, as it can be seen in Fig. 27, where the results of the INM measurements of the converter controlled with random spread spectrum PWM using the peak detector are presented. In contrast to the square signal in Fig. 16, here six specific frequency ranges can be highlighted. In Fig. 27, a high number of peaks and dips over the frequency under study are clearly seen. The I_{NM} of the DC/DC GaN converter controlled by random spread spectrum PWM is the most complex time-variant EMI within the framework of this paper. However, as shown in Fig. 27, the PDF for the first frequency range, from 18 kHz to 22 kHz, yields very similar results for the peak detectors of the receivers under study.

Table 10. E2.2.1 - Receivers comparison for the EMI from the converter controlled with continuous PWM.

Detector	R2/R8		R9/R8	
	Δ_{MAX} (dB)	Δ_{AVE} (dB)	Δ_{MAX} (dB)	Δ_{AVE} (dB)
PK	-0.43	-0.49	2.96	0.13
AV	-0.43	-0.50	-	-
QP	-0.70	-0.77	-	-

Fig. 27 E2.2.3 - The EMI from the converter controlled with random spread spectrum PWM.

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Fig. 28 E2.2.3 - The PDF of the EMI from the converter controlled with random spread spectrum PWM.

For both results of the E2.2.2 and E2.2.3 the analyses similar to the one used for the generated signals with time-variant frequency content are performed and listed in Table 11 and Table 12, respectively. The E2.2.2 results in the average deviation from the R2 output is less than 2 dB, for all detectors. The standard deviations are up to 1.17 dB. Meanwhile, for the emission from the DC/DC converter with random spread spectrum PWM, despite the measured signal’s complexity, the R2 results’ average deviation for all detectors is within 3 dB. It’s also quite remarkable that the differences between R9 and R8 are slightly larger than in pair R2/R8.

Table 11. E2.2.2 - Receivers comparison for the EMI from the converter controlled with linear spread spectrum PWM. Average deviations from R8.

Receiver	R9/R8		R2/R8	
Detector	PK	PK	AVE	QP
Δ MODE (dB)	-0.99	-1.24	-1.30	-2.22
\bar{d} (dB)	-1.21	-1.09	-1.09	-1.63
s_d (dB)	0.45	0.43	1.17	0.55

Table 12. E2.2.3 - Receivers comparison for the EMI from the converter controlled with random spread spectrum PWM. Average deviations from R8.

Receiver	R9/R8		R2/R8	
Detector	PK	PK	AVE	QP
Δ MODE (dB)	-2.49	-1.42	1.04	-2.45
\bar{d} (dB)	-2.63	-1.40	0.54	-2.44
s_d (dB)	2.53	2.72	2.80	1.53

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4. Measurement uncertainty

This section discusses the measurement uncertainty of the results presented in the previous sections. The different EMI receiver architectures generally lead to different measurement uncertainty components. EMC test laboratories usually do not perform complicated and time-consuming evaluations of the EMI receiver measurement uncertainty, and they depend on data from an accredited calibration laboratory or a datasheet of the manufacturer (as noted in Section 3). The measurement uncertainty analysis is divided into several sections in agreement with the designation of particular experiments in *Table 1*.

E0 – Calibration of EMI receivers using standard reference signals

The AV/PK/QP level reading accuracy is checked using a signal generator with a known output level. The main measurement uncertainty contributions include

- For a sine signal, the measurement uncertainty of a calibrated power meter is typically 0.05 dB to 0.1 dB.
- The impedance mismatch uncertainty between the power meter (power splitter) and the EMI receiver. For well impedance-matched devices, it is typically below 0.05 dB up to 1 GHz. The measurement uncertainty component due to impedance mismatch is given by $M_{dB} = 20 \log |1 \pm \Gamma_g \Gamma_{rec}|$, where Γ_g is the output reflection coefficient of the sine-wave generator (eventually the effective source match of the power splitter) and Γ_{rec} is the input reflection coefficient of the measuring receiver (measured or taken from manufacturer datasheet)
- Linearity of the EMI receiver is typically <0.01 dB (FD receivers) and <0.05 dB (oscilloscope-based EMI receivers).

E1.1 – Verifications using controlled modulated signals (pulse-modulated sine wave, CISPR B-D bands).

For the absolute and relative response to pulses measurement, one needs either a base-band pulse generator (the energy is spread in the whole frequency range of a particular CISPR band – not discussed in this report) or a pulse-modulated CW source (the energy is only spread in a close vicinity of the carrier frequency – recommended method for oscilloscope-based TD EMI receivers). The total measurement uncertainty when using a pulse-modulated CW source is composed of

- measurement uncertainty of the CW signal power (calibrated power meter, typ. 0.1 dB)
- measurement uncertainty due to non-ideal square-wave shape of the pulse modulator (there may be additional frequency components in the controlled modulated signal due to ringing or limited transition time of the pulse), typ. 0.1 dB
- if the amplitude of the pure sine-wave and the pulse-modulated sine-wave is not the same (can be validated using an oscilloscope), a correction factor should be applied to the measured QP detector level with uncertainty typ. 0.1 dB
- stability of the pulse duration (quality pulse modulator in modern signal generators allows for repeatable measurements), the measurement uncertainty component is typically <0.05 dB.
- Level measurement accuracy of the EMI receiver <0.05 dB.

E1.2 – Verifications using controlled modulated signals (alternative waveforms, CISPR A band).

The AWG LeCroy T3AFG120 contains a 16-bit digital-to-analog converter (3 dB bandwidth 120 MHz, 2 channels), which allows for very fine amplitude variations. The quantization level of the AWG is smaller or comparable to the quantization level of EMI receivers used in the report (see *Table 2*). The FD receivers use an ADC with 14-16 effective bits (the R&S ESW, ESPI, ESI), the TD receivers typically use ADCs with an effective number of bits 10-14 up to tens of MHz and 6-8 bits up to hundreds of MHz. The frequency accuracy

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of the T3AFG120 is superior when an external 10 MHz reference source is used. The measurement uncertainty budget contains the following contributions:

- AWG amplitude flatness is specified as ± 0.3 dB in the frequency range (0-100) MHz relative to a 10 kHz sine wave. All the experiments (see *Table 4*) were performed in CISPR band A (up to 150 kHz), thus the flatness error is negligible and can be estimated as < 0.05 dB.
- The dynamic range of TD EMI receivers (R&S RTO64, PS5444D) is < 70 dB due to the limited ADC resolution, and thus, the noise contribution could be more significant when calculating spectral properties than when using FD receivers. The measurement uncertainty component for RTO64 and PS5444D can be estimated as 0.2 dB for multitone and 0.1 dB for trapezoidal waveform.

E2 – Realistic emissions measurements.

The measurement uncertainty due to the measurement instrumentation is similar to controlled scenarios E0, E1.1, E1.2. The main measurement uncertainty contribution of realistic emissions scenarios is the measurement repeatability due to the stability of the emission source (DC/DC buck-boost converter, PWM stability). The larger deviations are also seen from Fig. 22, Fig. 23, Fig. 26, and Table 10 to Table 12. The measurement uncertainty due to the standard deviation of measured results can be as high as 1 dB to 3 dB.

5. Conclusion

Previous works have verified the performance of time-domain measuring receivers based on direct sampling instruments. However, the corresponding evidence remained scattered and focused either on calibration data or specific use cases. This study bridged that gap by providing a sequence of validations through a multi-level approach. In five different experiments, commercial EMI receivers (frequency-swept and FFT-based) were compared with an oscilloscope-based counterpart (R1 and R2) following an approach where the complexity of the excitation signals increased progressively. Based on the results obtained, it is concluded that R1 and R2 performed as well as their CISPR 16-1-1 compliant counterparts in the frequency and amplitude ranges evaluated; that is, the measurement errors in various test conditions remained well within standard tolerances. The measurement uncertainty of each measurement scenario was evaluated based on known specifications of the devices (calibration certificates or manufacturer datasheets). It is essential to recall that this is the first work where such multi-level and extensive empirical validation has been explicitly carried out, in collaboration with independent teams, to benchmark direct sampling implementations of FFT-based measuring receivers with commercial solutions.

It is expected that this work will contribute to leveraging EMC standardization by supporting the explicit mention of EMI receivers based on direct sampling instruments. Widening the measuring receiver definition in this way would open up a broad range of possibilities for new measurement setups based on multi-channel and full time-domain capabilities. Such features, explored in several research projects, offer advantages that are well-suited for widespread applications in EMC practice.

In conclusion, Deliverable 4 of EMC-STD project has been successfully achieved and this document meets the objective 2 requirements committed in Annex 1 JRP Protocol.

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